

Monitoring of Damage-induced Impact Force for Composite Laminates Using PVDF Sensor Signals

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ABSTRACT

Several techniques for monitoring the impact response of composite structure with sensors were proposed by many researchers. However, the inverse techniques to reconstruct impact force are limited to low energy impact problem which no damage occur during impact event. Based on the previous research results for the effect of impact damage on the structures, the possibility for reconstructing damage-induced impact force using PVDF (polyvinylidene fluoride) film sensor signals without considering microdamage were examined. In this paper, the PVDF film sensor was attached on the surface of symmetric cross ply graphite/epoxy laminate. A series of low-velocity impact tests from low energy to damage-induced energy were performed. The numerical and experimental verification for simulating sensor signals and reconstructing impact forces were performed for the forward and inverse impact problems. The measured signals of PVDF sensor agreed well with the simulated signals based on the linear relationship between the impact force and the sensor signal when the damage due to low-velocity impact was local. The damage-induced impact forces can be reconstructed from PVDF sensor signals based on the linear elastic model ignoring local impact damage.

KEYWORDS: low-velocity impact, PVDF film sensor, damage-induced impact, composite laminates, inverse problem

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of advanced composite materials in main structures of military and civil aircrafts has increased rapidly because of their considerable advantages over conventional metals in high specific strength and stiffness. However, composite structures are susceptible to damage from low-velocity impact, which can produce significant subsurface damages (matrix cracks, delaminations, and fiber breakages) while leaving little or no external visible evidence. Thus, the damage resistance and the damage tolerance of composite structures for low-velocity impact are the major substantiation items for aircraft certification process [1]. Conventional structural integrity inspections of aircraft, which require downtime and use nondestructive methods such as ultrasonic imaging or X-radiography, are very labor intensive and prone to human error. Therefore, a health monitoring system for aircraft structures should include the ability to detect impact events and damage they cause.

Several techniques for monitoring the impact response of composite structure with sensors were proposed by many researchers [2-6]. Doyle [2] used the spectrum analysis method to reconstruct the impact force from the strain gage signal for a specially orthotropic plate. Kim and Hahn [3,4] used iterated regularization method to reconstruct the impact force from PVDF sensor signals for fabric graphite/epoxy plate. Yen and Wu [5,6] used the optimization technique to identify the impact force and the impact location for isotropic plate using the strain gage signals. But, most of the inverse techniques to reconstruct impact force are limited to low energy impact problem which no damage occur during impact event.

Fortunately, there were some papers that described the effects of impact damage on the structures. Lagace [7] noted that the global response of composite laminates was the dynamic response under impact force and wasn't affected by local impact damage. Tracy [8] showed that local impact damage caused a small reduction in overall bending stiffness and the frequency shifts of high order bending

modes meant the presence of impact damage. And, Olsson [9] noted that delaminations and matrix cracks had a negligible influence on the stiffness and significant stiffness reductions were only observed in a small central region of the thin laminates where fiber failure had occurred.

Based on these research results, the possibility for reconstructing damage-induced impact force using PVDF (polyvinylidene fluoride) film sensor signals without considering microdamage were examined. In this paper, the PVDF film sensor was attached on the surface of symmetric cross ply graphite/epoxy laminate. A series of low-velocity impact tests from low energy to damage-induced energy were performed. The numerical and experimental verification for simulating sensor signals and reconstructing impact forces were performed for the forward and inverse impact problems using this model.

2. ANALYSIS

The governing equation for composite laminates under impact force was derived using the assumed mode method with the Mindlin plate theory [4,6,10]. When the point force, $p(t)$ applied transversely on the panel at (x_0, y_0) , the displacement and strain at arbitrary point (x_1, y_1) are expressed as

$$w(x_1, y_1, t) = \int_0^t p(t - \tau) G_w(x_1, y_1, \tau; x_0, y_0) d\tau \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_\xi(x_1, y_1, t) = \int_0^t p(t - \tau) G_{\varepsilon_\xi}(x_1, y_1, \tau; x_0, y_0) d\tau \quad (2)$$

where $w(x_1, y_1, t)$ and $\varepsilon_\xi(x_1, y_1, t)$ are the transverse displacement and in-plane strain of arbitrary point (x_1, y_1) at time t , respectively. G_w and G_{ε_ξ} are the impact response function for the transverse displacement and the in-plane strain of the surface along ξ (x or y) direction, respectively.

When a PVDF film with effective area A_p and thickness t_p is subjected to in-plane strain ε_x and ε_y , the charge developed in the film is given by Q and the corresponding open circuit voltage \bar{V} is then

$$\bar{V} = \frac{Q}{C_p} = \frac{1}{A_p} \int_{A_p} (C_x \varepsilon_x + C_y \varepsilon_y) dA \quad (3)$$

where sensor constant, C_x and C_y are defined as

$$C_x = \frac{t_p}{\varepsilon_{33}} e_{31} \quad \text{and} \quad C_y = \frac{t_p}{\varepsilon_{33}} e_{32}$$

and ε_{33} is the permittivity in the thickness direction, e_{31} and e_{32} are the piezoelectric constants of the PVDF sensor. In this study, C_p is $1,363 \times 10^{-12}$ F, C_x is 14,223(V/strain), and C_y is 6,278(V/strain).

Numerical integration was used to solve the convolution integral equations (Eqs. (1) and (2)). The integral equation is then reduced to set of L equations. The interval of integration $(0, t)$ is divided into L equal subintervals of width $\Delta\tau = t/L$. Eqs. (2) and (3) has further been discretized into a matrix equation of the following form [4,6].

$$\{\mathbf{V}\} = [\mathbf{G}]\{\mathbf{p}\} \quad (4)$$

where $[\mathbf{G}]$ is L by L matrix and $\{\mathbf{V}\}$ is the measured voltage of the PVDF sensor. In Eq. (4), $[\mathbf{G}]$ is the transfer matrix which obtained by combining the piezoelectric constitutive equation of the sensor with the approximate equation of motion for the plate based on assumed-mode method and by discretizing these integral equations into an matrix form. In this study, 10 by 10 modes were used in x and y direction, respectively.

In the forward problem, displacements and strains can be simulated using measured impact force. In the inverse problem, in order to solve for the impact force $\{\mathbf{p}\}$, measured sensor signal $\{\mathbf{V}\}$ and inverse of the transfer matrix $[\mathbf{G}]$ are needed. But, the inverse of $[\mathbf{G}]$ is ill-posed. Unfortunately, small errors in measured signals cause a large fluctuation in the solution. This means that an exact solution from the measured signals cannot be obtained. For the inverse of the transfer matrix $[\mathbf{G}]$, it is necessary to regularize it. The iterated Tikhonov regularization method [4,10,12] was used in this paper,

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The experimental set-up is shown in Fig. 1. The drop weight impact tester was used to induce impact on composite laminates. The laminate panels were impacted normal to the surface by dropping the instrumented impactor (force transducer, PCB M208A33) which the steel impactor tup (PCB 084A19) had hemispherical nose and a diameter of 12.7 mm. Impact force and sensor signals were digitized by AD converter and recorded for the further analysis.

Fig. 1 Experimental set-up

The specimens used in this study are solid laminated panels made of graphite/epoxy fabric prepreg (HT145/RS1212, HFG). The panel dimensions were 262.5×137.5 mm and stacking sequence was $[0/90]_{4S}$. Each specimen was placed on a rigid support and simply supported around four edge by a steel fixture. This provides a 250 mm by 125 mm test area. Two strain gages and a PVDF sensor with 30 mm long by 12 mm wide and $28 \mu\text{m}$ thick were mounted on the surface of the laminate with epoxy resin as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Specimen geometry and sensor locations

Table 1 presents a summary of the impact test matrix. 16 impact tests (4 different impact masses, 5 different impact heights) were conducted on Gr/Ep Laminates. The energy of impact was calculated from the height of free fall multiplied by weight of the impactor. Some friction loss along the guide rail was neglected.

Table 1 Impact test matrix and impact energy

Test No.	Mass (gr)	Height (mm)	Energy (J)	Remarks
1	125	100	0.123	
2		300	0.368	
3		600	0.735	
4		900	1.103	
5		1,200	1.470	
6	503	100	0.493	
7		300	1.479	
8		600	2.958	
9		900	4.436	
10		1,200	5.915	
11	1,301	100	1.275	
12		300	3.825	
13		600	7.650	
14		900	11.475	damage
15		1,200	15.300	damage
16	2,004	900	17.675	damage

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Forward problem

For the forward problem, the signals of the PVDF sensor were simulated using the measured impact forces. In this study, four different impact masses were used. Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show the PVDF sensor signals. The contact duration increased as the impact mass became heavier. For the same mass, the contact durations wasn't changed, but the matrix cracks increased the contact duration. Matrix cracks on the back face were observed for the conditions above the 11.5 J of impact energy. The permanent deformation shape of test 14, and 2-dimensional delamination shape of test 16 was observed. The damage area measured by the ultrasonic C-scan shows an oval shape in Fig. 5. The damage area calculated from the ultrasonic C-scan was about 1.5 % of the panel area in the case of test 15. For the test 16, the damage area was almost 2% of the panel area. All of the delaminations were observed near the matrix cracks of the back face.

Fig. 3 Measured PVDF sensor signals for different impact mass at impact height=900mm

Fig. 4 Measured PVDF sensor signals of impact mass=1,301gr for different height

Fig. 5 C-Scan image of test 15 (Damage area; 24×18mm)

The good agreement between simulated sensor signals and measured signals of the PVDF sensor were shown in Fig.6 although the simulation results were computed using Eq. (2) which didn't consider the degradation occurred by impact damage. It means that the local damage does not affect the global response of the laminate. There were some discrepancies in sensor signals at unloading region of the damaged laminates. These discrepancies increased as the impact damage grew. The measured signals of the damaged laminates showed local high frequency signals greater than 5 KHz during the contact duration. These high frequency signals were found near the maximum impact force. These signals implied the damage initiation and propagation of the laminates [13,14,15]. At present, it was difficult to evaluate the signals quantitatively.

(a) Impact mass=503gr, height=300mm

(b) Impact mass=1,301gr, height=1,200mm

Fig. 6 Measured and simulated PVDF sensor signals

4.2 Inverse problem

For the inverse problem, the impact forces were reconstructed using the measured signals of the PVDF sensor. The reconstructed forces from measured sensor signals are compared with the measured impact forces in Fig. 7. There are some deviations in the low energy impact conditions, but most of impact test show good agreement. There are two reasons for such deviations, first of all, because of the ill-posed nature of the transfer matrix, the inversion process is sensitive to even small variations in the signal due to the low signal to noise ratio. Therefore, slight change in the signal can lead to the reconstruction of a quite different impact force. The second reason is that the transfer matrix was derived under the assumption of linear-elastic behavior without damage and hence is not truly representative of the actual behavior. Combined together, these two factors make the inverse prediction rather precarious. Fortunately, however, the reconstructed impact forces are not much sensitive to the local damage than expected. The reconstructed impact forces under the higher impact energy condition showed good agreement with the measured signals. Although highly fluctuating impact forces with small amplitude due to specimen stiffness loss as a result of damage was observed in Fig. 6, (b) and (c), it may be difficult to reconstruct the high frequency components of impact force using current linear elastic relation between force and strain based on assumed mode method. However, the global shapes of the reconstructed impact force history including the impact durations and the maximum impact forces, showed good agreement with measured signals. It means that the

impact force can be reconstructed using the PVDF sensor signals in spite of the existence of local damage.

(a) Impact mass=503gr, height=1,200mm

(b) Impact mass=1,301gr, height=900mm

(c) Impact mass=2,004gr, height=900mm

Fig. 7 Measured and reconstructed impact force

5. CONCLUSIONS

An impact monitoring system based on the use of a discrete number of sensor requires an efficient signal process algorithm that can predict impact force from the sensor signal. The forward and inverse problem for the damage-induced impact of graphite/epoxy laminates using PVDF film sensor signals were examined. Both experimental and analytical work were conducted. The experimental correlation led to the following conclusions:

1. The measured signals of PVDF sensor agreed well with the simulated signals based on the linear relationship between the impact force and the sensor signal when the damage due to low-velocity impact was local.
2. The damage-induced impact forces can be reconstructed from PVDF sensor signals based on the linear elastic model ignoring impact damage and an iterated Tikhonov regularization method can be used for this inverse problem.

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